

ISSUES OF DEVELOPING TOLERANCE THINKING IN FUTURE SOCIAL WORKERS

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information on reforms to improve the social life of society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks of social workers and the development of their tolerant mindset.

Keywords: social work, worker, tolerance, reform, thinking, life, task, development, knowledge, politics, stability, law.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasidagi jamiyatning ijtimoiy hayotini yaxshilash to'g'risidagi islohotlar, iltimoiy ish xodimlarining vazifalari va ularning tolerantlik tafakkurini rivojlantirish masalalari haqidagi ma'lumotlar batafsil yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy ish, xodim, tolerantlik, islohot, tafakkur, hayot, vazifa, taraqqiyot, bilim, siyosat, barqaror, huquq.

Аннотация: В статье дается подробная информация о реформах по совершенствованию социальной жизни общества в Республике Узбекистан, задачах социальных работников, развитию у них толерантного мышления.

Ключевые слова: социальная работа, работник, толерантность, реформа, мышление, жизнь, задача, развитие, знание, политика, устойчивое, закон.

Based on the principles aimed at the interests of our citizens, who are the main factor in the development and rise of the country, centuries-old innovations are being implemented in our country, which our compatriots see in the positive changes in their lives and lifestyles.

This indicates that our people fully support the reforms being implemented to build a new Uzbekistan. At the same time, in the updated constitutional and legal conditions, it is necessary to improve the main directions of our country's development and bring the ongoing large-scale reforms to a new level.

To realize the will of our people to build a free, prosperous, powerful New Uzbekistan, to create all opportunities for each citizen to develop their potential, to raise a healthy, educated and spiritually mature generation, to form a strong economy that has become an important link in global production, to ensure justice, the rule of law, security and stability.

In particular, today, the establishment of Social Work Departments in higher educational institutions in order to improve the social life of society is

being manifested as a form of state social policy aimed directly at improving the social lifestyle of people. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev's Decree No. PF-82 dated June 1, 2023 "On comprehensive measures to provide high-quality social services and assistance to the population and establish an effective control system for them"[1], Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-319 dated September 28, 2023 "On measures to further improve the system of providing social services and assistance to the population"[2], Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 654 dated October 21, 2021 "On measures to further improve the system of social protection of the population" and other regulatory and legal documents indicate the relevance of this area.[3]

The demand for social workers in this area has been developing for a long time, but special training of specialists in this field began to develop in Western Europe in the 19th-20th centuries. One of the main reasons for this is the high level of socialization in society and the emergence of the need for a social worker. The first teacher in life for a person is need and experience. It is these that bring a person to the level of distinguishing between useful and harmful things. When the need for certain things increases in society, a demand for them appears.[4] Social work is a professional activity aimed at helping and supporting people in resolving interpersonal relationships and facilitating social changes in society, in order to improve their well-being.

The main tasks of a social worker The social worker performs the following main tasks:

- raising awareness of the population about social services and assistance, as well as social work activities;
- organizing the provision of social services and assistance to persons in need of social protection;[5]
- conducting a preliminary assessment to open a "social case" on his own initiative in urgent cases, as well as to open a "social case" based on the application of persons in need of social protection and draw up an individual social services plan;
- drawing up a short-term individual social assistance plan for persons in need of social protection, if necessary; explaining to the population about social services and assistance guaranteed by the state, as well as the rights of the population to receive these services;[6]
- taking comprehensive measures to solve the problems of persons in need of social protection in cooperation with the chairman of the makhalla citizens'

assembly, assistant, prevention inspector, women's activist, youth leader, etc.; involvement of internal resources, including social support volunteers (relatives, neighbors, volunteers) in the provision of social services and assistance and coordination of their activities in this regard;

- study of the real situation in families, including assessing the needs of the population for social protection.[7]

In conclusion, the issue of spirituality is an important issue for every society. High spiritual qualities are the most important factor in achieving success in the professional activities of social workers. In turn, if a social worker demonstrates his spiritual qualities in the team, social workers with a good reputation become an example of spiritual maturity for the environment as an element of the whole society.

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